

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 23:0 A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>1 מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד יְהוָה רֹעִי לֹא</p>
<p>Psa. 23:1 The LORD is my “shepherd,</p>	<p>אֶחָסֵד : 2 בְּנֵאֻת דָּשָׂא יְרֻבִיצְנִי</p>
<p>I ¹shall ^bnot want.</p>	<p>עַל־מִי מִנְחֹת יִנְהַלְנִי : 3 נִפְשִׁי</p>
<p>² He makes me lie down in “green pastures;</p>	<p>יִשׁוּבֵב יִנְחֵנִי בְּמַעְגְלֵי־צֹדֵק</p>
<p>He ^bleads me beside ^{1c}quiet waters.</p>	<p>לְמַעַן שָׁמוּ : 4 גַּם כִּי־אֵלֶיךָ</p>
<p>³ He “restores my soul;</p>	<p>בָּגִיא צְלֻמוֹת לֹא־אֵירָא רָע</p>
<p>He ^bguides me in the ^{1c}paths of righteousness</p>	<p>כִּי־אַתָּה עֲמֹדֵי שִׁבְטֶךָ</p>
<p>For His name's sake.</p>	<p>וְמִשְׁעֵנֶיךָ תִּמָּה יִנְחֵמְנִי : 5</p>
<p>Psa. 23:4 Even though I “walk through the ¹valley of the shadow of death,</p>	<p>תַּעֲרֹךְ לְפָנַי אִשְׁלֶחַן נֶגֶד צָרָרֵי</p>
<p>I ^bfear no ²evil, for ^cYou are with me;</p>	<p>דִּשְׁנֹת בַּשֶּׁמֶן רֹאשִׁי כּוֹסֵי רוּחָה :</p>
<p>Your ^drod and Your staff, they comfort me.</p>	<p>6 אֵךְ אִטּוֹב וְחָסֵד יְרַדְפוּנִי כָּל־</p>
<p>⁵ You “prepare a table before me in the presence of my enemies;</p>	<p>יָמֵי תַיִי וְשִׁבְתֵי בְּבֵית־יְהוָה</p>
<p>You ¹have ^banointed my head with oil;</p>	<p>לְאַרְךָ יָמִים :</p>
<p>My ^ccup overflows.</p>	
<p>⁶ ¹Surely “goodness and lovingkindness will follow me all the days of my life,</p>	
<p>And I will ^{2b}dwell in the house of the LORD ³forever.</p>	

References

<p>Psalm 23:1 ¹Or <i>do</i> ^aPs 78:52; 80:1; Is 40:11; Jer 31:10; Ezek 34:11-13; John 10:11; 1 Pet 2:25 ^bPs 34:9, 10; Phil 4:19</p> <p>Psalm 23:2 ¹Lit <i>waters of rest</i> ^aPs 65:11-13; Ezek 34:14 ^bRev 7:17 ^cPs 36:8; 46:4</p> <p>Psalm 23:3 ¹Lit <i>tracks</i> ^aPs 19:7 ^bPs 5:8; 31:3 ^cPs 85:13; Prov 4:11; 8:20</p> <p>Psalm 23:4 ¹Or <i>valley of deep darkness</i> ²Or <i>harm</i> ^aJob 10:21, 22; Ps 107:14 ^bPs 3:6; 27:1 ^cPs 16:8; Is 43:2 ^dMic 7:14</p> <p>Psalm 23:5 ¹Or <i>anoint</i> ^aPs 78:19 ^bPs 92:10; Luke 7:46 ^cPs 16:5</p>	<p>Psalm 23:6 ¹Or <i>Only</i> ²Another reading is <i>return to</i> ³Lit <i>for length of days</i> ^aPs 25:7, 10 ^bPs 27:4-6</p>
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Targum

Psa. 23:1 A psalm of David. It is the LORD who fed his people in the wilderness; they did not lack anything. ² In a place of thirst he will settle me in pleasant grass; he led me to the waters of rest. ³ He will restore my soul with manna; he led me in the paths of righteousness for the sake of his name. ⁴ Indeed, when I go into exile by the plain of the shadow of death, I will fear no evil; for your word is my help, your straight staff and your Torah, they will comfort me. ⁵ You have set before me a high table of manna in front of my oppressors; you have fattened my body with stuffed fowl, and with anointing oil [you have fattened] the heads of my priests; my goblet is wide. ⁶ Indeed grace and favor will follow me all the days of my life, while I sit in the sanctuary of the LORD for length of days.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

David was being chased by Saul's men, who intended to kill him. For David, it was a dark and discouraging period in his life. He hid in the Hereth forest (1 Sam 22:5). This forest was a barren, desolate forest, parched and dry. The LORD did not abandon David. He soaked the dry forest with moisture that had the flavor of the world to come, making the grass and leaves of the forest succulent and edible (this can be found in the Midrash).

This psalm is customarily said between the washing of the hands and offering the blessing over the bread. This custom can be explained using Gematria. There are fifty-seven words in the psalm, the numerical equivalent to the word "nourishes." In addition, there are 227 letters in the psalm, which is equivalent to the word "blessing." Reciting and living by the words of this psalm offers a blessed life with ample provisions.

Verse One

מְזִמֹּר לְדָוִד (meez'mor l'david) – means "a psalm of David." This short superscript is not in the English versions of the psalm. The Hebrew and Targum verses do include it. This phrase is a part of verse one.

רֹעֵי (roer) – means "feed, pasture." Why does the NASB use the word "shepherd?"

The English translations tend to use church-accepted language when there is a

discrepancy. The Septuagint (LXX Brenton translation) says, "The Lord tends me as a shepherd, and I shall want nothing." This is probably where the shepherd language originated for the church. The Targum in English says, "It is the LORD who fed his people in the wilderness; they did not lack anything." The shepherd's job was to ensure that his flock of sheep was fed. Hirsch and Steinsaltz use the translation shepherd.

The translation from the Targum is a more accurate translation when it is read with the background of the Midrash. The LORD brought moisture and food to the Hereth forest so that David could survive. He needed food and water in this forest. Where was he going to find it? Since that was impossible, the LORD gave him the food and water he needed. The LORD did the same thing for the Israelites while they roamed in the desert of Sinai. The LORD brought moisture and manna from Heaven for the people. The custom of reciting the psalm between the washing of hands and the blessing over bread is a reminder of the miracle of manna and to remember that the LORD will provide the basic needs. David acknowledged the LORD's gifts to his ancestors and to him.

A psalm of David. It is the LORD who fed his people in the wilderness; they did not lack anything.

Verse two

בְּנֵאוֹת (been'ot) – means "in the pastures." This word is derived from the Aramaic word for "beautiful, pleasant." An additional "vuv" is added to the Aramaic word, and the result is the word for "pleasant places, pastures." Therefore, the translation of "pleasant place" can be used. For a flock of sheep, a pleasant place is a pasture. The Targum adds the words "in a place of thirst." When the sheep move from an old water source to a new water source, they become thirsty. The shepherd is aware of this

situation and knows where the water holes are and whether his sheep can reach them before they die from dehydration. The LORD made the Hereth forest a pleasant place for David by bringing water and food to him.

In my thirst, He will settle me in pleasant grass; he leads me to the peaceful waters to rest.

Verse three

נֶפֶשׁ (naph'shee) – means "soul." This is a broad translation. In the spiritual understanding of the soul, there are five parts.

1. Nefesh
2. Ruach
3. Neshama
4. Chaya
5. Yechida

The Nefesh in the Kabbalah is considered the soul's flesh while in Malkhut (Earthly kingdom). Therefore, in this verse, the spiritual awareness is the understanding that the restoration of the soul is restoring David's body. He required food, water, and especially rest. He had been running away from Saul's troops and was exhausted when he reached the Hereth forest. The LORD rejuvenated his body with the three items already mentioned.

Using the Nefesh part of the soul, the spiritual awareness translation is:

Again and again, He gives my flesh food, water, and rest; He also leads me in the paths of righteous justice for His Name's sake.

Verse four

The shadow of death that David was walking through was his fleeing path from Saul. If the soldiers caught David, they would have murdered him on the spot. David placed his faith and trust in the LORD, knowing that the LORD would save him since he was anointed to be the next King of Israel.

When I go into exile through the valley overshadowed by death, I fear no evil because You are with me; Your rod and Your staff comfort me.

Verse five

David said that the LORD gives peace and inner calmness amid suffering. David felt safe in the Hereth forest because the LORD had led him there. He can enjoy the respite that he needed. This is what is meant by the phrase "you prepare a table before me in the presence of my enemy." The anointed is a reminder that Samuel anointed David as the next King of Israel. The cup is the cup of destiny. It is full because David knows what the LORD expects of him, and he knew what his future was to be.

You prepare a table for me even though my oppressors are near because you protect me; you had me anointed as your King with oil; my destiny has been foretold, and you will see that it happens.

Verse Six

David calls out to the Sefirah Chesed, knowing that Chesed's loving kindness will be with him all his days.

Indeed the Sefirah Chesed will bless me all the days of my life, and I will return into the house of the LORD for all time.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A psalm of David. It is the LORD who fed his people in the wilderness; they did not lack anything.

In my thirst, He will settle me in pleasant grass; he leads me to the peaceful waters to rest.

Again and again, He gives my flesh food, water, and rest; He also leads me in the paths of righteous justice for His Name's sake.

When I go into exile through the valley overshadowed by death, I fear no evil because You are with me; Your rod and Your staff comfort me.

You prepare a table for me even though my oppressors are near because you protect me; you had me anointed as your King with oil; my destiny has been foretold, and you will see that it happens.

Indeed the Sefirah Chesed will bless me all the days of my life, and I will return into the house of the LORD for all time.

Appendix

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Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

